

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Negotiation through an Ethical Lens: The dilemma ‘to deceive or to be deceived’

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ABSTRACT

People negotiate throughout their daily lives, whether for business, trade, or simply to accomplish something. People may be inclined to use deception during negotiations because each individual has an inherent tendency to maximize their advantage to prevent being deceived. At the bargaining table, negotiators continually experience this idea. This paper aims to find out why people use deception at the negotiation table by reviewing the existing literature on this issue using the qualitative research method to collect data mainly from secondary sources, like books, research articles, and other publications. This article also sheds light on when negotiators are most likely to use deception, and what psychological dilemmas negotiators generally experience while dealing with deception at the negotiation table. It also focuses on the future area of research in this field of study to analyze the relationship between negotiation and deception in general and how deception often effects negotiation..

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1. Introduction

In daily encounters, people must negotiate to gain an edge by taking use of the information provided by the other side, and they may also have a propensity to mislead in order to avoid being deceived. So, negotiation and deception are immanent in our lives (Olekals & Smith, 2009). According to Dinctopal et al. (2007), people frequently believe that they are less likely to act completely morally to further their own interests, and even the most sophisticated moral reasoning is not always effective in stopping this conduct. They also mentioned how an excellent negotiation is typically necessary for business success and how dealing with the intimidating and immoral business environment presents people

with difficult ethical dilemmas. In negotiation, people use a variety of strategies such as cheating, deception, and providing non-existent or false information, which can be seen as ethically acceptable or unethical depending on who you're negotiating with (Fulmer, Bruce & Long, 2009). Generally, negotiations are characterized by uneven and crooked information, and most of the time, the negotiators mislead their counterparts in order to catch better incentives and opportunities (Gaspar & Schweitzer, 2012). A competent negotiator must assess the possibility of being fooled, respond when they notice a deceitful attitude toward his rival, and maintain control at the negotiating table by using effective techniques rather than deception (Gaspar & Schweitzer, 2012). In addition, most people are not expert enough to identify the lie in negotiation (Bond & De Paulo 2006). Accordingly, negotiations are satiated with incentives and opportunities for the use of deception (Schweitzer & Croson, 1999). Sometimes parties have inadequate information about one another's likings and possible alternatives, leaving ample room to deceive and be deceived (Mason, Wiley & Ames, 2018). Sometimes negotiators frequently present misinformation or wrong information to achieve the incentive (Mason, Wiley & Ames, 2018). These opportunities, however, may also entail high costs; deception, if revealed, might damage trust (Schweitzer, Hershey & Bradlow, 2006) and reputations (Raiffa, 1982). So, the paper delves into how deception frequently influences negotiation as well as the relationship between deception and negotiation more broadly. It mainly relies on a literature review to pinpoint the common tensions between being deceived and deceiving others. By highlighting the future areas of study in this field, this article also sheds light on the rationale for utilizing deception in negotiations and the ethicality of such deceptive practices.

2. Defining Ethics and Negotiation

Negotiation is one of the best alternative forms of dispute resolution. In terms of negotiation, the question of ethics is always inbuilt. In general, ethics refers to a collection of social behaviors or standards that define what is right and what is wrong in a given context, as well as a method for establishing those behaviors and standards (Gordon, 2017, October). It grows out of particular values which define the nature of the world

where we live and prescribe rules for living together (Gordon, 2017, October). Ethics is based on well-founded ideals and standards of right and wrong that suggest what humans should and should not do, usually in the context of rights, obligations, societal advantages, justice, or specific qualities (Moberg & Velazquez, 2009). Some years ago, a renowned sociologist Raymond C. Baumhart asked business people, "What does an ethic mean to you?" In summary, according to their responses, ethics is divided into two categories. To begin with, ethics refers to well-founded moral norms that dictate what humans should do. Second, the study and development of one's ethical ideals is referred to as ethics (Moberg & Velazquez, 2009). As previously stated, sentiments, laws, and social conventions can all diverge from ethical behavior. Ethics also entails a never-ending effort to examine our own moral views and conduct, as well as a desire to ensure that we, and the institutions we help form, adhere to reasonable and well-founded norms (Moberg & Velazquez, 2009).

A negotiation, like ethics, entails several aspects; one of them is persuading others to believe in the authenticity or sincerity of facts that would influence their decision. Negotiation is a channel of communication between two or more people or parties with the goal of reaching an understanding, resolving a disagreement, or increasing benefit as a result of dialogue, producing an agreement on courses of action, bargaining for individual or collective benefit, and crafting outcomes to satisfy the various interests of the two people/parties involved in the negotiation process. Furthermore, negotiation is a process in which each party attempts to acquire an advantage for themselves at the conclusion of the process. In truth, the goal of negotiation is to reach a compromise (J. Lewicki, 2017). It is also interpreted as a pleasure of the needs of both parties with a just division of what is obtained and what is not obtained (Nermin, 2010). It also indicates a communication process in the style of one step forward, one step back—with the sole objective of reaching a decision (Maddux, 1988). Moreover, it is a voluntary process that involves different actors with different interests or goals, different attitudes, and strategies leading to a situation where people are trying to adjust these differences in order to reach an agreement (Alavoine & Batazzi 2013). In a negotiation, each party must work together to achieve their objectives, and each party can prevent the

other from attaining their objectives (L., 1990). This dependency creates a mixed-motive connection in which both sides collaborate while competing for opposing goals (L. & M.E., 1992). In order to attain maximum benefit from a deal, negotiators often use different tactics, some of which may be unethical, like deceiving the counterpart through misrepresenting, misleading, or showing a furious and evasive attitude.

3. Deception in negotiation

Using deception in negotiation is not a new mechanism. The negotiator's uses of deception in the negotiations can be traced at least to a narrative from the Old Testament, in which Laban fools Jacob, his stepson, into believing that if Jacob works for six years for his stepfather, he will be rewarded by being able to marry Laban's youngest daughter, Rachel. Jacob fulfills his end of the bargain, yet when it comes to Laban's turn to marry off his daughter, it becomes clear that he had presented misinformation from the start (Holy Bible. Genesis 29, Chapter 31). For maximizing the negotiator's benefits, the use of deception is very common in negotiation. DePaulo et al. (1996), in their research found that the average people tell between one to two lies daily. On the other hand, in terms of negotiation, when the incentives are great, more than 55% of negotiators use active forms of deception (Aquino & Becker, 2005). Moreover, in 1996 Murnighan, Babcock, Thompson, & Pillutla found that over a third of negotiators with high levels of experience used deception in a single negotiation (Murnighan et al. 1999). Generally, in terms of labor negotiations, corporate mergers, salary negotiations, and global climate change negotiations, the existence of deception is wide-ranging (Ma & Parks, 2012). In general, job seekers occasionally use dishonest and deceptive negotiation tactics during salary discussions since these negotiations are so difficult and intensive. This was true even if they had no intention of deceiving or defrauding a potential employer. For instance, the job seeker received an alluring offer to work as the director of innovation for a developing start-up company after searching for a new position for several months. As the conversation continues, the recruiting manager inquires as to whether the job candidate has any other offers pending. The job applicant may be claiming to have "many firm offers", despite the fact that they have no other offers. When the manager presses for details, the job seeker tells the manager that the other offers

are “significantly higher” than the one the company has made PON Staff. (2018, December). Like this salary negotiation, a similar pattern of negotiation is more or less seen in every negotiation.

4. The ‘to be deceived or to deceive’ in negotiation dilemma

In negotiation “to be deceived or to deceive” is the most ethical confrontation almost every

negotiator faces. At the negotiation table, negotiators always tend to negotiate to maximize profits. When both parties are very tough in negotiation, and the negotiating matter is most propitious, this kind of dilemma usually arises.

Negotiators often don't say everything they're thinking (Jones, 2017, July 12) and sometimes they hold back or distort information to avoid being exploited by the other party (Alavoine & and Batazzi, 2013). In a negotiation, the parties come to the table with more than just strategies and tactics to address a particular situation with clear goals in mind. They also bring with them norms, values, and beliefs that may be different from those of the other party but will affect how they view the circumstances (Alavoine & and Batazzi, 2013). Conflicts between values and practices that they think should be used or things used by their opponents sometimes confuse the general negotiator (Alavoine & and Batazzi, 2013).

Normally there are four major approaches or lenses in negotiation ethics (PON Staff, 2018, December). They are as follows:

i. End-result ethics (results lens):

This is the Machiavellian approach's slogan, and it suggests that if the end of a particular action is good, we can put up with the methods we used to get there (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). The rightness of an action is resolute by appraising its consequences (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). On the other hand, it can be said that the end result justifies the means. To achieve the much-desired end result, sometimes negotiators use different kinds of unethical techniques. In terms of negotiation, these unethical methods are sometimes admitted as deception. In this scenario, a question like "what will be the outcome?" might be asked (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March).

- ii. **Duty ethics (reputation lens):** The rightness of an action is determined by an individual obligation to adhere to consistent principles, laws, and social standards that define what is right and wrong (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). When it comes to using deception or truth at the negotiating table, the individual reputation index has a considerable impact on the other party. "What will others think?" is a question that emerges at this point." (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March).
- iii. **Social contract ethics (relationship lens):** The rightness of an action is based on the tradition, customs, and norms of a particular society or community (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). The adoption of deceitful tactics by a negotiator is heavily influenced by the societal norms and beliefs of that person. This raises the issue, "How will this affect others?" (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March).
- iv. **Personality ethics (rights lens):** The rightness of the action is based on individual conscience and moral standards (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). If the ethical standard or integrity of an individual is so high, normally, S/he does not use deceptive techniques in negotiation. Here the question arises: "what should I do?" (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March).

The above-mentioned moral lenses in terms of using truth or deception are always in the mind of negotiators. At the negotiation table, every individual falls in a quandary of being deceived or deceiving. So in an ethical predicament, such questions as i) What will be the result, ii) What will others think, iii) How will this impact others, iv) What should I do? So on and so forth are frequently peeping into the mind of the negotiators at the negotiation table (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March).

Like the above-mentioned ethical questions in negotiation, there are other major dimensions or dilemmas of ethical conduct:

i. Truth telling v. Concealment of information dilemma

Telling the truth or suppressing information at the negotiation table has a meaningful impact on the outcome of a negotiation. So, negotiators usually face the dilemma of whether they should tell the truth or withhold the information in negotiation. In reality, telling the truth is an essential topic in ethical behavior, particularly in medical

ethics. For example, there is a patient diagnosed with cancer in its late stages, and he expresses that he doesn't want to know the truth if the results of his tests are bad (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). Should the doctors tell him the truth or withhold the information? (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). It's probably the best if he doesn't know what really has happened in this circumstance (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). The patient, on the other hand, has a right to know about his health (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). So, dilemmas relating to disclosing the truth or telling untruth or partial truth is important in terms of negotiation because that ultimately triggers the negotiators to be deceived or to deceive.

In fact, speaking the truth or giving facts is regarded as one of the most important aspects of any negotiation. Sharing information demonstrates mutual trust and understanding, which may result in a better negotiation conclusion (Volkema, 2004). Furthermore, because knowledge is viewed as a source of power, the more information a side has, the more powerful and dominant its stance becomes (Volkema, 2004). Therefore, every so often, negotiators experience the dilemma of how much information to share with another party. This information can be of two categories, valid/relevant and invalid/irrelevant (Volkema, 2004). Exchanging invalid/irrelevant data and information occurs when negotiators distort facts, make false promises, bluff, or deceive, which is regarded as one of the unethical strategies used by negotiators to secure or protect their position at the bargaining table (Volkema, 2004).

ii. Sins of omission v. Sins of commission dilemma

Schweitzer and Croson, in their study, found that in negotiations, people who commit sins of omission have better distributive outcomes than those who do not use deception (Schweitzer & Croson, 1999). Similarly, people who commit sins of commission outperform those who do sins of omission as well as those who act honestly (Schweitzer & Croson, 1999). This suggests that in a single negotiation in which the parties will not engage in a recurring negotiation relationship, the employment of commission sins will be the prevailing tactic (Jeff, 2016). All in all, those who use deception have been demonstrated to be effective in negotiations since their

competitors are frequently unaware of their dishonesty (Jeff, 2016). Thus, negotiators often face the dilemma of sins of omission and sins of commission. While both parties are very strong at the negotiation table, the negotiators face the above-mentioned dilemma. Sometimes they think that using sins of commission would maximize their incentives rather than using sins of omission in the negotiation.

iii. Absolutism v. Relativism dilemma

In terms of negotiation, absolutism and relativism are the two extreme ethical approaches, while negotiators are both valid and supported by facts, but they are quite contrary to each other in views (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). According to absolutism, everything in the world is certain, and there is a universal moral standard for all human beings and society (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). On the other hand, relativism is more idiosyncratic (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). An ethical absolutist believes that there is a single or universal moral standard for the whole society, and everybody must conform to this standard (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). If two persons in society differ about whether something is acceptable or not, according to the absolutist position, one of them must be at fault, because ethical principles are universal (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). Relativists, on the other hand, hold the opposite viewpoint. They believe that exceptions to moral standards may be necessary in specific circumstances (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). In contrast to absolutists, relativists think that if two individuals in society are in conflict about something, if it is right or wrong, they can be both right or both wrong because there is nothing like an absolute universal moral standard (Dinctopal et al., 2007, March). As a result, the determinant of deceptive or non-deceptive behavior, as well as individual ideas of ethicality and unethicity, such as absolutism and relativism, vary from person to person in terms of negotiation. Negotiators frequently face the difficulty of being deceived or deceiving at the bargaining table in their own world of absolutism and relativism.

iv. Good reputation v. Bad reputation dilemma

This is one of the vital dilemmas for negotiators, where one decides to use deception in negotiation or to act in an honest manner can be thought of as a two-layered process, in which the individual first

considers what the counterpart might do, then decides how to respond (Jeff, 2016). In a normal salary negotiation, an employer might think to himself, "If I think my new employee would lie, then I ought to lie," or "If I think my new employee might not lie, then I ought to speak the truth." Similarly, the employer may have a similar perception of whether the new hire is being truthful (Jeff, 2016).

The saturated decision tree would look as follows:

Figure 1: Saturated decision tree (Jeff, 2016).

In the above graph, we can see four different scenarios in which the employer must decide how to respond if he believes the new employee will be truthful or if he believes the counterpart will be truthful (Jeff, 2016). However, the negative reputation condition fundamentally changes how the principal or employer is likely to use truth or adopt a falsehood (Jeff, 2016),. If the employer suspects the new employee of lying, the decision tree is altered to:

Figure 2: Decision tree when the employer believes the counterpart will lie (Jeff, 2016),

The above graph indicates that the employer has solid reason to suspect that the new employee will lie to him, and as a result, the employer's ethical decision-making is based on a completely different set of circumstances (Jeff, 2016). As seen in the picture

above, the employer has a good reason to believe that the new employee will lie to him, and as a result, the employer's ethical decision-making is based on an entirely different set of facts (Jeff, 2016),

However, the decision tree might be reversed if the counterpart has a positive reputation. The following is the principal's decision tree, with the counterpart in the good reputation condition:

Figure 3: Decision tree when the principal believes the counterpart will tell the truth (Jeff, 2016).

In the graph shown above, it is seen that in a positive reputation condition, the principal is likely to believe that the new employee is going to act in an honest manner. Because of the fairness heuristic and equity theory, the principal is more inclined to act honestly (Jeff, 2016). As a result, negotiators at the table are constantly confronted with the reputation dilemma: principals or employers who negotiate with a counterpart or employee who has a bad reputation are more likely to use deception than principals or employers who negotiate with counterparts who have a good reputation (Jeff, 2016).

v. **Principal v. Agent dilemma**

The principal and agent dilemma is one of the most basic psychological challenges in negotiation. When an agent gets to a negotiating situation, the other party or counterpart may assume that the agent is concealing something, exaggerating something, or just telling half-truths, or that the agent is looking for a profit from the negotiation. Similarly, if the relationship between the principal and the agent isn't strong enough, the principal may suspect the agent of deceit for personal advantage, despite the fact that the agent works

for the principal. At the negotiation table, these principal-agent dilemmas are always on negotiators' minds.

In the situation mentioned above, the negotiators always fall into a quandary of being deceived or to deceiving in negotiation.

5. Reasons for choosing unethical behavior in negotiation

Negotiation practitioners and scholars have long believed that at least tacitly, unethical behavior and negotiation go hand in hand. To put it in another way, many people with different perspectives on negotiation believe that ethical behavior is nearly hard to be avoided in negotiating situations (Gunia, 2018). It may be argued that where there is a negotiation process, there will be lies and deception. In addition, academics have noted the ubiquity of dishonesty in negotiations, with some coming to the conclusion that deception occurs in the majority, if not the vast majority, of situations (Aquino, 1998). Individuals with great moral character are naturally prone to ethical negotiation, rejecting the pull of unethical activity despite the fact that it may pay off financially (Gunia, 2018). Certain predictable characteristics of the negotiating situation (such as incentives and competitiveness) may cause ethical fading, leading to restricted ethicality among negotiators (Gunia, 2018). Similarly, certain predictable aspects of the physical and temporal context in which negotiators operate (e.g., money, time of day) might produce distributive and misleading bargaining strategies (Gunia, 2018).

The desire to outbid an opponent in a competitive situation, as well as the necessity to ensure or restore some norm of justice that has been broken, are the three primary motivating factors that lead negotiators to consider using unethical tactics. There are so many reasons behind choosing the unethical act of deception in negotiation.

Firstly, the allure of temptation is the main reason behind using the deception at the negotiation table. The value of the reward affects a negotiator's willingness to behave unethically throughout the negotiation process. It works the way enticement affects morality and induces immorality. The greater the magnitude, the more probable it is that the negotiators will accept it. (PON Staff. (2022, April). Furthermore, the more desirable the position, the more likely the candidate is to fabricate

superior offers. Our ethical standards appear to be less rigid than we would like to believe (PON Staff. (2022, April).

Secondly, uncertainty makes it more likely that the negotiators will act unethically. In a negotiation, uncertainty regarding the material facts might lead to unethical behavior (PON Staff. (2022, April). Negotiators who were less confident gave more aggressive, less honest estimates than those who were more confident (PON Staff. (2022, April). Uncertainty over the prospect of a better offer appears to raise the likelihood that a job applicant will fraudulently pretend to have other offers during a job negotiation (PON Staff. (2022, April).

Thirdly, the negotiators who are less powerful are more inclined to act unethically to overcome their barriers (PON Staff. (2022, April). Outside alternatives to a deal can be a significant source of bargaining leverage. In their investigation, Northwestern University's Tenbrunsel and David Messick discovered that a lack of external options encourages the negotiator to lie (PON Staff. (2022, April). In one experiment, the participants pretended to be managers negotiating with potential clients (PON Staff. (2022, April). A negotiator who chooses to utilize an immoral strategy usually does so in order to gain negotiation leverage. By changing the perceived foundation of factual information (lying), gaining greater information about an opponent's plan, or diminishing an opponent's capacity to achieve his aims, power can be obtained (PON Staff. (2022, April). Using these strategies has two outcomes: i) actual achievement or non-achievement of the goals he sought; and ii) evaluation and criticism of the tactics by the negotiator, his opponent, and the spectator (PON Staff. (2022, April). Negotiators frequently feel obligated to defend their conduct, i.e., they are aware that they have done something "bad" and need to provide a "good justification (PON Staff. (2022, April).

Fourthly, we discovered that negotiators regard group interactions as less personal than individual interactions, which they believe justifies increased unethical behavior while dealing with groups (PON Staff. (2022, April). In the same way dealing with difficult people, managing the counterpart's satisfaction with the negotiator's own satisfaction, and the needs of the bargaining counterpart may influence the ethical and

unethical behavior in the negotiation (PON Staff. (2022, April). So the terms "ethical conduct" and "means/ends," "truth-telling," and "relativism" were employed to characterize a wide range of problematic negotiating strategies and tactics (Dinctopal, et al.,2007, March). Some negotiators believe that bluffing, misrepresentation, or factual distortion is sometimes necessary for successful negotiations; nevertheless, others may see such behavior as immoral and unacceptable (Dinctopal, et al.,2007, March).

There are also a good number of factors that can affect the use of unethical tactics, including the background and demographic characteristics of negotiators, the personality characteristics, and elements of the social context that encourage or discourage unethical behavior within the negotiation context (Lewicki, Barry & Saunders, 2010). People's individual cultural norms and values play a pivotal role in terms of the application of ethical and unethical strategies in a given situation. People who are collectivists usually trust and cooperate with their in-group members, but they compete with out-group members (Hsu,1983). In contrast, people who are individualistic in nature and belong to an individualistic societal culture do not make distinctions between in-group and out-group members, and the way they negotiate more likely depends on the strategy their counterparts choose rather than one belonging to in- or out-group (Vasylenko, 2011). Furthermore, people from high-avoidance cultures are skeptical of newcomers, whereas people from low-avoidance cultures are more welcoming (Hofstede, 1980). Furthermore, perceived appropriateness and the likelihood of engaging in competitive and dubious negotiation activities are closely related to power gap. People from high power distance cultures are more tolerant of unethical behavior such as bribery and cheating, and hence are more likely to adopt unethical negotiation strategies than people from individualistic cultures (Getz & Volkema, 2001). Furthermore, cultural differences such as masculinity and feminism may have a significant impact on people's behavior. Even if we all want a fair, competitive, and fruitful negotiation at any table, individual conduct plays a key role in the use of ethical and unethical techniques against one's opponent.

As a result, differences in their backgrounds, personalities, rewards or punishments associated with ethical or unethical actions, and social and cultural norms that dictate what is appropriate or inappropriate in a given environment may all influence the negotiators' decision to use ethical or unethical tactics to varying degrees (PON Staff, 2018, October).

After all, while there are a variety of reasons why negotiators use unethical or misleading tactics, the three most commonly cited motivations are greed, competition, and perceived injustice Murnighan, J. K. (1991). To begin with, it is thought that a person's motivation to improve his/her personal outcome may outweigh his/her desire to be fair and cooperative (Murnighan, 1991). Secondly, despite everything, most negotiators strive to outperform their peers (Murnighan, 1991). Thirdly, if a negotiator has been treated unfairly, he or she may retaliate by lying (Murnighan, 1991). Furthermore, when another side does not know the true size of the shared pie, such as in ultimatum bargaining games, negotiators are more likely to mislead. When people participate in ultimatum bargaining games, they offer substantially less money to their opponents because they are unaware of the true amount of money divided (Vasylenko, 2011).

6. Ethicality of using deception in negotiation

Every negotiating process, it is widely assumed, incorporates ethical issues in some way. Someone claims that negotiation should be viewed as a game rather than a win-win transaction that satisfies both sides' needs with a fair distribution of what is acquired and what is not obtained. So, in the course of the negotiation, the questions of i) what is fair? ii) What is the definition of justice? iii) What does it mean to be legal? 4) What constitutes proper and acceptable behavior? And, last, what should be expected to the other party in negotiation? The negotiators' minds are always on strike. A negotiator, like the Poker Player, seeks to facilitate his opponent's incorrect evaluation in a variety of ways. In this situation, some ethical behavioral questions arise, such as: what is practical? What is the most practical solution? What does it mean to be efficient? What is in one's or a client's best interests? What does it take to win? and the lie., the negotiator is perplexed. In reality, the ability to both deceive and not be misled is the crucial distinction

between effective negotiators and those who are not (Cramton & Dees, 1993).

The ethicality of using deception in negotiations varies from context to context and person to person. In a game like poker, what could be acceptable in-game theory is unlikely to be acceptable in all negotiation scenarios. Similarly, what is accepted in Washington may not be acceptable in the Middle East. Individual cultures have natural norms on what constitutes appropriate bluffing or misrepresentation and to what extent. Differences in individual backgrounds, personality, rewards or punishments associated with ethical or unethical actions, and social and cultural norms that dictate what is appropriate or inappropriate in a given environment can all influence the decision to use ethical or unethical tactics to varying degrees (Dinctop et al. (2007, March). So, the question of ethicality and unethicality in terms of negotiation is situation based.

From their own perspective, there are three types of believers who believe in utilizing deception in negotiation. Adherents of the 'game theory' believe that deception is usually acceptable since negotiation is like a game of poker where players must make decisions based on tradeoffs and uncertainty. In negotiations, a degree of deceit and dishonesty is both typical and expected. Negotiators are said to have to use every trick in the book to fool their opponent, or else risk being duped and defeated in return (Mason, Wiley & Ames, 2018). Pragmatists, on the other hand, analyze the costs and benefits of deceit in negotiation, keeping both material welfare and moral values in mind, and then decide how to act, such as lying, cooperating, and so on (Mason, Wiley & Ames, 2018). Finally, idealists adhere to high ethical and integrity standards in negotiations, as well as in all other areas of professional life where ethics and integrity should be applied (Mason, Wiley & Ames, 2018).

The quandary of "to be deceived or to deceive" is a very common one in negotiations because deception is regularly resorted to there. One group thinks that lying during a negotiation is just a game, as when you're playing poker. On the other hand, some professionals feel that lying in negotiations should be avoided. Nonetheless, there is a heated discussion concerning which sorts of deceit are permissible in negotiations and

which should be avoided. Misrepresentation of one's bottom line price is not a problem, but misrepresentation of material information is (Jeff, 2016). So, the ethicality or acceptability of deception is always a debatable issue in terms of negotiation.

7. Consequence of deception in negotiation

Using deception in negotiation is inherently a risky proposition (Jeff, 2016). As regards unethical negotiations, many studies have found numerous negative consequences of deception for both the deceiver and the deceived (Gunia, 2018). Although deceptive negotiators may extract some short-term benefits (Cramton & Dees, 1993), deception is generally perceived to be quite detrimental (Gunia, 2018). Those who utilize deception frequently do so at their risk (Jeff, 2016). The recurrent practice of deception can lead to a doubtful reputation, which can be challenging to reverse (Jeff, 2016). Whenever the deception is discovered, it hampers business relationships (Lewicki & Hanke, 2012) and leads to a disentanglement of negotiations (Olekals & Smith, 2007), creating a loss-loss situation for both negotiating parties (Jeff, 2016). Moreover, it diminishes trust (Rogers et al., 2016), stimulates vengeance (Boles, Croson & Murnighan, 2000) and harms the deceiver's pecuniary upshots (Croson, Boles & Murnighan, 2003). The following graph depicts the outcomes of a series of unethical negotiation practices:

Figure: Effects of unethical behavior in negotiation (Dinctopal et al. 2007, March).

Here, the X-axis signifies the total 30 minutes time of three consecutive negotiations, duration of 10 minutes for each. The Y-axis indicates the negotiation success through using unethical behavior in negotiation. As time passes, success increases through unethical behavior, and it sets a bad trend!

In a very short time, the negotiator can be very successful, which is shown in the first two negotiation phases, but in the third phase, it shows total failure in negotiation. So, in a short period of time, even if the negotiators might gain success, the ultimate result is not a pleasant one. In fact, this too is problematic and harmful, at least for the deceived and probably for the deceiver (Gunia, 2018).

Deception can have serious legal ramifications, in addition to the negative repercussions on business and reputation (Jeff, 2016). Furthermore, the United States Supreme Court established the "Honest Claim" theory in *NLRB v. Truitt Mfg. Co.*, 351 U.S. 149 (1956), which requires that parties in labor negotiations work in good faith and that any claims made by any party be honest (Jeff, 2016). Furthermore, the factors that are the subject of deceit in many negotiations, such as delivery date, promised quality, the number of personnel who will be used in a project, and so on, can be checked and used as evidence in deception cases (Reilly, 2008).

Despite the fact that many negotiators utilize deception in the hope of never being detected and achieving better negotiating outcomes (Gaspar & Schweitzer, 2013), when they are found, they lose in all areas of business, and their reputation suffers as a result.

8. Conclusion

Negotiation is not a competitive game, despite the fact that negotiators employ numerous immoral strategies to maximize their eventual gain. In a negotiation, negotiators solely focus on seeing the other parties as adversaries for the sake of a short-term gain, and thereby jeopardize their long-term reputation. To get rid of the dilemma- 'to be deceived or to deceive', and to evaluate the appropriate strategies and tactics, the negotiators should keep in mind and understand the ethical reasoning, such as end-result ethics, the principles of utilitarianism, rule ethics, the principle of rule utilitarianism; social contract ethics, the principles of community-based socially acceptable behavior, personalist ethics, and the principles of determining what is right or what is wrong in the light of one's own conscience. As negotiators have differing interests and the outcomes that negotiators opt for deception, further research is needed to examine how a negotiator's personal characteristics trigger the counterpart to adopt deceptive behavior in negotiation.

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Declaration of Interests

I, the authors of this research manuscript, declare that I have no financial interest. I have provided written consent to publish the paper in this journal.

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